

Playback the music of the brain - decoding emotions elicited by music in the human brain

Version 0

Description

This DMP describes the data management procedures implement in the "Playback the music of the brain - decoding emotions elicited by music in the human brain" project.

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Researchers

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Organizations

Centro de Imagem Biomédica e Investigação Translacional, Universidade de Coimbra

Datasets

Title: Neural correlates of music listening

Template: FCT - Template in English

Raw MRI data, physiological data and metadata using BIDS standard acquired during a music listening paradigm.

Dataset Description

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

No

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

mixed media (image and textual)

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

structural and functional human brain imaging (BIDS standard) - .nii, .json and .tsv files

This project is based on brain imaging: the dataset will be saved in the BIDS format (The specification is intentionally based on simple file formats and folder structures to reflect current lab practices and make it accessible to a wide range of scientists coming from different backgrounds - BIDS is developed by the community for the community and everybody can become a part of the community, for more information, please consult <https://bids.neuroimaging.io/>)

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

>1000 GB

We aim to acquire data from approximately 50 participants - each participant requires 2 GB

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

Following the BIDS standard, we will add .json and .tsv sidecar files that include information regarding several details of the dataset, including participants, dataset, and task (according to the standard these files are named dataset-description.json, participants.json, participants.tsv).

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

Yes

2.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data.

.tsv files with structured information regarding the task, and acquisition parameters for each session (data regarding details of the task performed by each participant such as events onset and duration - this information is key for statistical data analysis). .json files with a structured information on the acquisition parameters (filename example for participant 01, session 01, run 01 - "sub-01_ses-01_run-1_T1w.json").

2.2.3 Please identify the metadata standard(s) that apply.

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

2.2.4 Please identify the controlled vocabularies that apply.

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Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS)

2.2.5 Please select the appropriate language for metadata.

eng

3.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.1.1 Describe where the data and metadata will be stored during the project.

Institution networked research storage

3.1.3 Is there a policy in place for data backups during the project?

No

The institution has a centralized VNA infrastructure (commercial solution by Siemens) that implements redundancy. There is no policy on data backup (either on-site and/or off-site). The raw data is kept in its original form in the VNA, and data is copied for statistical analysis.

3.2 Protection and security of sensitive data

3.2.1 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

Additional security measures (please specify)

4.1 How will you handle issues regarding the processing of personal information and intellectual property rights and ownership?

4.1.1 Will you process and/or store personal data during your project?

Yes

4.1.2 How will compliance with legislation and (institutional) regulation on personal data be ensured?

All participants signed an informed consent before data acquisition (previously approved by an ethics committee). Raw data is stored in a certified, commercial solution (Vendor Neutral Archive) with access policies in-place - Only approved personnel has access to project's data. All secondary copies (data extracted) is pseudo-anonymized. Only the Principal Investigator (PI) has access to the conversion table (id - project code). The table will be destroyed after the project end.

4.1.3 How will ownership of the data and intellectual property rights to the data be managed?

Bruno Direito

University of Coimbra

Data will be stored at CIBIT, a research unit of the University of Coimbra. Data managing duties are responsibility of the PI, Bruno Direito. Data is owned by the University of Coimbra.

5.1 Long-term data preservation

5.1.1 How will data be selected for long-term preservation?

All data resulting from the project will be preserved for at least 10 years

5.2 Data available for re-use

5.2.1 What data will be made available for re-use?

All data resulting from the project will be made available

5.2.3 When will the data be available for re-use, and for how long will the data be available?

Data available as soon as article is published

We will publish the data without restrictions as soon as the first publication is published in a open peer-reviewed journal.

5.2.4 In which repository will the data be archived and made available for re-use, and under which license?

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OpenNeuro

5.2.5 Please confirm if:

- The repository is registered in the re3data directory
- The repository is aggregated in OpenAIRE

5.2.6 Please indicate whether a persistent identifier will be pursued.

Yes

doi

5.2.7 Under which license will the data be archived and made available for re-use?

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

CC0

2023-06-30

5.2.8 Describe your strategy for publishing the analysis software that will be generated in this project.

All processing scripts will be published in our institutional GitHub account - <https://github.com/CIBIT-UC>.

6.1 Responsibilities and resources for data management

6.1.1 Who (for example role, position, and institution) will be responsible for data management?

- Bruno Direito
- Ana Rodrigues

Universidade de Coimbra Instituto de Ciências Nucleares Aplicadas à Saúde

Bruno Direito is responsible for data acquisition and data quality assurance and Ana Rodrigues is responsible for checking compliance with regulatory aspects.

6.1.2 What resources (for example financial and time) will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)?

Considering the volume of data and current practices of the institution, most data managing tasks have been included in internal procedures and guidelines.

Title: Questionnaire on a music listening task

Template: FCT - Template in English

Categorization of music excerpts based on the affection model (valence and arousal)

Dataset Description

1.1 What existing data will be re-used?

1.1.1 Will you re-use existing data for this project?

Yes

1.1.2 Which existing data you will re-use and under which terms of use?

We will use the music excerpts dataset proposed by Panda et al. (2020). Panda, Renato, Ricardo Malheiro, and Rui Pedro Paiva. "Novel Audio Features for Music Emotion Recognition." IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing 11, no. 4 (October 1, 2020): 614-26. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAFFC.2018.2820691>.

1.1.3 Describe the data type you will re-use

audio

1.1.4 Describe the format of data you will re-use

wav

music files format

1.2 What data will be created or produced?

1.2.1 Will new data be created in this project?

Yes

1.2.2 Describe the data you expect your research will generate.

mixed media (textual)

1.2.3 Describe the data format you expect your research will generate.

.csv files

This project is based on the characterization of music excerpts and their neural correlates based on functional magnetic resonance imaging. We will save behavioral information (participants categorization of the stimuli) in csv files.

1.3 What is the data volume?

1.3.1 How much data storage will your project require in total?

0 - 10 GB

We aim to acquire data from approximately 50 participants - each participant requires 1MB

2.1 Documentation

2.1.1 Indicate what documentation will accompany the data.

We will add a README.md file explaining the variables and data acquisition protocol.

2.2 Metadata

2.2.1 Is there metadata associated with the data?

No

2.2.4 Please identify the controlled vocabularies that apply.

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